

Supporting Information

The fitness landscape of a form II rubisco in a photosynthetic bacterium guides engineering of oxygen tolerance

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Supp. Fig 1. (related to Fig. 1) Alignment of parts of the sequence of *Gallionella* sp. (*Gallionella*) Form II Rubisco with homologous parts of Form I Rubiscos of *Spinacia oleracea* (*Spinacia*), *Synechocystis* sp. PCC 6803 (*Synechocystis*), *Synechococcus* sp. PCC 6301 (*Synechococcus*), *Thermosynechococcus kodakarensis* ATCC BAA-918 (*Thermosynechococcus*), *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (*Chlamydomonas*), *Cupriavidus necator* (*C. necator*), Form II Rubiscos of *Rhodospirillum rubrum* (*R. rubrum*), *Rhodopseudomonas palustris* ATCC BAA-98 (*R. palustris*), *Gallionella* GWSB1 (primary accession A0A0X1KHE5) as well as Form III Rubiscos of *Archaeoglobus fulgidus* ATCC 49558 (*A. fulgidus*) and *Methanococcoides burtonii* DSM 6242 (*M. burtonii*). Shades of blue indicate degrees of similarity. *Gallionella* residue positions included in the large library are indicated by arrows. Numbers above the alignment give the absolute position in the complete alignment.

Gallionella 2 - - - - - MD-QSNRYADLSLKEEDLIKGGNHILVAYTMEPAAGVG-YLEAAAHIAAESSTGTNVEVSTTD--EFTKRGVDALVYFIDEAK--
R. palustris - - - - - MD-QSNRYANLNKESLIIAGGRHILVAYTMEPAAGVG-YLEAAAHIAAESSTGTNVEVSTTD--DFTRGVDAALVVEIDEAN--
Gallionella - - - - - MD-QSNRYANLNKESLIIAGGRHILVAYTMEPAAGVG-YLEAAAHIAAESSTGTNVEVSTTD--DFTRGVDAALVVEIDEATAFG
R. rubrum - - - - - MD-QSNRYANLNKESLIIAGGRHILVAYTMEPAAGVG-YLEAAAHIAAESSTGTNVEVSTTD--DFTRGVDAALVVEIDEATAFG
M. burtonii - - - - - MSLLIYEDLVKSLDSKQAYVDLKLPPD--TNGEFLIYAFHMI PGGDIL-VLQAAEIAAESSTGTNIVKISSET--AFSRMTNARVQLDLER--
T. kodakarensis - - - - - MVKFDIYDYVVDKGYEYPSKRRDIIIVFRVTPAEYTT-IEQAAAGAVAAESSTGTWTLVYPWYEQERWADLSAKAYDFHDMG--
A. fulgidus - - - - - MAEFEIYREYVVDKSYEP-QKDDIVAVFRITPAEGFT-IEDAAGAVAAESSTGTWTLVYPWYDEERVAKLSAKAYDFVLDL--
Thermosynechococcus - - - - - MAYTQSKQKVGQAGVKDYRLT-VYTPDYTP-KDTDI LAAFRVTPQEPVP-PEEAAAVAAESSTGTWTVVWTDL-LTDLDRYKGCCTIEPLPGE
Spinacia - - - - - MSPQTEKASVEFKAGVKDYRLT-VYTPDYTP-KDTDI LAAFRVTPQEPVP-PEEAAAVAAESSTGTWTVVWTDL-LTDLDRYKGCCTIEPLPGE
Synechocystis - - - - - MPKTQS--AAGYKAGVKDYRLT-VYTPDYTP-KDTDI LAAFRVTPQEPVP-PEEAAAVAAESSTGTWTVVWTDL-LTDLDRYKGCCTIEPLPGE
Synechococcus - - - - - MVQAQAGFKAGVKDYRLT-VYTPDYTP-KDTDL LACFRMTPQEPVP-PEEAAAVAAESSTGTWTVVWTDL-LTDLDRYKGCCTIEPLPGE
Chlamydomonas - - - - - MVPQTEKAGAGVKDYRLT-VYTPDYTP-KDTDI LAAFRMTPQEPVP-PEEAAAVAAESSTGTWTVVWTDL-LTDLDRYKGCCTIEPLPGE
C. necator MNAPEIQAQPKRYDAGVMKYKEMGWDDGYVP-KTDVLALERIITPQDEVD-PVEAAAAGAVESSTIATWTVVWTDL-LTACDMYRAKAKARVDPVPPN

Gallionella 2 - - - - - GIMKVAYPNDLFDNRNVDGRVMIVSFLTLCIGNNQGMGDIANLQMQDFYVPPRMLQLFDGPAKDIISDLWRILGRPVKGGYISGTIIKPKLGL
R. palustris - - - - - SLMKIAYPIELFDRNVIDGRAMIASFLLTIGNNQGMGDEYAKMYDFYVPPAYLKLFDGPAKDIISDLWRILGRPVINGGFI VGTIIKPKLGL
GallionellaDDPVKGGGLFKVAYPVELFDRNVIDGRAMIASFLLTIGNNQGMGDEYAKMYDFYVPPAYLKLFDGPAKDIISDLWRILGRPVINGGFI VGTIIKPKLGL
R. rubrum - - - - - ELTKIAYPVALFHRNITDGKAMIASFLTIGNNQGMGDEYAKMYDFYVPPAYLKLFDGPAKDIISDLWRILGRPVINGGFI VGTIIKPKLGL
M. burtonii - - - - - ELVWJAYPWRFLDR-----GGNVQNI LTVIIGNILGNKE IQALKLMDFWFP SMLQYDGP SYTVDDMRKYLDVYDRP----LGTIVKPKMGL
T. kodakarensis - - - - - DGSWIVRIAYPFAHFE-----ANLPLGLASIAIGNFGMKRVKGLRLEDLYFBEKLIREFDGPAGFIEGRKMLEIKDRP----IYGVVPPKPVGY
A. fulgidus - - - - - DGSIVRIAYPSELFEF-----HNPGLASIAIGNFGMKRVKGLRLEDLYFBEKLIREFDGPAGFIEGRKMLEIKDRP----IYGVVPPKPVGY
Thermosynechococcus - - - - - DNQFIAYIAYPLDLFE-----GSVTNMLTSIVGNVFGKALKALRLEDLRIYVAYLKTFOGPHGIVQERDKLNKGRP----LLGCTI KPKLGL
Spinacia - - - - - ENQYICYAYPLDLFE-----GSVTNMLTSIVGNVFGKALKALRLEDLRIYVAYLKTFOGPHGIVQERDKLNKGRP----LLGCTI KPKLGL
Synechocystis - - - - - ENSYFAFIAYPLDLFE-----GSVTNMLTSIVGNVFGKALKALRLEDLRIYVAYLKTFOGPHGIVQERDKLNKGRP----LLGCTI KPKLGL
Synechococcus - - - - - DNQYFAFIAYPLDLFE-----GSVTNMLTSIVGNVFGKALKALRLEDLRIYVAYLKTFOGPHGIVQERDKLNKGRP----LLGCTI KPKLGL
Chlamydomonas - - - - - DNQYIAYVAYPIDLFE-----GSVTNMLTSIVGNVFGKALKALRLEDLRIYVAYLKTFOGPHGIVQERDKLNKGRP----LLGCTI KPKLGL
C. necator PEQFFCYVAYPIDLFE-----GSVTNMLTSIVGNVFGKALKALRLEDLRIYVAYLKTFOGPHGIVQERDKLNKGRP----LLGCTI KPKLGL

Gallionella 2 RPEPFKAAVQFWLGG-DFIKNDEPQGNQVFCPIKKVLPVYDLSLKRQDETGOAKLFSMNI TADDDHYEMCARADFALETFG--PDADKVAFLVDG FVGG
R. palustris RPPQFANACYDFWLG-DFIKNDEPQGNQVFCPIKKVLPVYDLSLKRQDETGOAKLFSMNI TADDDHYEMCARADFALETFG--DNADHIAFLVDGYVAG
Gallionella RPPFKAACYDFWLG-DFIKNDEPQGNQVFCPIKKVLPVYDLSLKRQDETGOAKLFSMNI TADDDHYEMCARADFALETFG--ENASHVALLVDG FVGG
R. rubrum RPKFAEACHAFLWGG-DFIKNDEPQGNQVFCPIKKVLPVYDLSLKRQDETGOAKLFSMNI TADDDHYEMCARADFALETFG--ENASHVALLVDG FVGG
M. burtonii T SAEYAEVYDFWVGGDFVKNDEPQGNQVFCPIKKVLPVYDLSLKRQDETGOAKLFSMNI TADDDHYEMCARADFALETFG--EPGSAFLVDG FVGG
A. fulgidus SAEVEKLA YELSGMDYIKDDENLTSPAYCFEERAEERIMKVIEKVEAETGEKSWFANITADLLEMEQRLEVLADLGLK-----HAMVDVITG
Thermosynechococcus SAKNYGRAVYECLELGGDLFTKDDENINSQPQRWRDRFLVADAIHKQAETGEIKGHYLNVTAPTCEEMKRAEFKALEMP-----HVWVDVITG
Spinacia SAKNYGRAVYECLELGGDLFTKDDENINSQPQRWRDRFLVADAIHKQAETGEIKGHYLNVTAPTCEEMKRAEFKALEMP-----IIMHDFLTAG
Synechocystis SAKNYGRAVYECLELGGDLFTKDDENINSQPQRWRDRFLVADAIHKQAETGEIKGHYLNVTAPTCEEMKRAEFKALEMP-----IIMHDFLTAG
Synechococcus SAKNYGRAVYECLELGGDLFTKDDENINSQPQRWRDRFLVADAIHKQAETGEIKGHYLNVTAPTCEEMKRAEFKALEMP-----IIMHDFLTAG
Chlamydomonas SAKNYGRAVYECLELGGDLFTKDDENINSQPQRWRDRFLVADAIHKQAETGEIKGHYLNVTAPTCEEMKRAEFKALEMP-----IIMHDFLTAG
C. necator GRNYGRVYVEGLKGLDFMKDDENINSQPQRWRDRFLVADAIHKQAETGEIKGHYLNVTAPTCEEMKRAEFKALEMP-----IIMHDFLTAG

H127 M140 H251

Gallionella 2 P GMVTTARRQYP -- SQY LHY HRAGHGMVT SPSSKRGYTA FV LAKMSRLQGA SGIHV GTMGYGRMEGG -- KDDRIIAYMIERD SGTGPFYHDEWY --
 R. palustris P AAVTTARRAFP -- KQY LHY HRAGHGAVT SPQSKRGYTA FV LSKMARLQGA SGIHT GTMGYGRMEGG -- AADRIAYMITEDAADGPYFHDEWL --
 Gallionella P AGVTTARRFP -- DTF LHFHRAGHGAVT SYKSPMGMDL CYMKLV LMGASGMT GTMGYGRMEGH -- GKETVLA YMLERDCQGPYFYQKQY --
 R. rubrum A AIIITARRFP -- DNFLHYHRAGHGAVT SPQSKRGYTA FV HCKMARLQGA SGIHT GTMGYGRMEGG -- SSDRIAYMLTQDEAQQGPFYRQSWG --
 M. burtonii WMVQTLRRRYP -- DVFLHFHRAGHGAVT RQENPIGFSLV LSKFARLQGA SGIHT GTAGI GRMKGTP -- AEDVVAASH IQYLKSPGHFFETWSKI
 T. kodakarensis WGALRYIRDLAADYGLA IHGHRAMHAAFT RNPYHGISMFV LAKLYLIGIDQLHVGTAGAKLGGKWDV IQNARI RE SHYKPDENDVFHLEK FYS --
 A. fulgidus WGALEYIRDLAEDYDLA IHGHRAMHAAFT R - NAKHGI SMFV LAKLYRIIGIDQLHI GTAGAGKLE GQKWDTVQNAR I F SEVEYTPDEGDA FHL SQN FHH --
 Thermosynochococcus FTANTLSKWRDNGML LHI HRAMHAAVMDR - QKNHGIHERV LAKCLRMSGGDHIHT GTV - VGLGDKAVT LGFV D LLRENY IEQDR SRGIYFTQD WAS --
 Spinacia FTANTLSHYCRDNGLL LHI HRAMHAAVMDR - QKNHGIHERV LAKALRSGGDHLSHTV - VGLGDKAVT LGFV D LLRENY IEQDR SRGIYFTQD WAS --
 Synechocystis FTANTLARWCRDNGV L LHI HRAMHAAVMDR - QRNHGIHERV LAKCLRSGGDHLSHTV - VGLGDKAVT LGFV D LLRENY IEQDR SRGIYFTQD WAS --
 Synechococcus FTANTLARWCRDNGI L LHI HRAMHAAVMDR - QKNHGIHERV LAKCLRSGGDHLSHTV - VGLGDKAVT LGFV D LLRENY IEQDR SRGIYFTQD WAS --
 Chlamydomonas FTANTSLA IYCRDNGLL LHI HRAMHAAVMDR - QRNHGIHERV LAKALRMSGGDHLHSHTV - VGLGDKAVT LGFV D LLRENY IEQDR SRGIYFTQD WAS --
 C. necator WTCIQSMSNWCQRNDMILHL HRAGHGTYR QKNHGVSE RVI IAKWLLR LAGVDHMT GTA VGLGDKAVT LGFV D LLRENY IEQDR SRGIYFTQD WAS --

Gallionella 2 - - - - - GMKPTTPIISGGMNA LRLP GFFENLGHGNNV INTAGGGSYGHIDSPAAAGAVSLRQAYECWKAGAD - - - - -
 R. palustris - - - - - GMPPTPIISGGMNA LRLP GFFDNLGHSNL IMTAGGGA FGHVDEGAA GAKSLRQAEQCKWQAGAD - - - - -
 Gallionella - - - - - GMKATPIISGGMNA LRLP GFQNLGHNV INTCGGAFGHIDSPAAAGGSLGQAYDCWKSGSD - - - - -
 R. rubrum - - - - - GMKACTPIISGGMNA LRLP GFFENLGHANV ILTAGGGA FGHIDPVA GARSLRQAWQWRDQVGP - - - - -
 M. burtonii MDTDKVDKVINLVNEDLAHV I LE DSSWRAMKCCPIVSGG LNPVKLPFIDVMENVD IITMGSVHSHPGGTS GAKLVQA CDAYLQGMV - - - - -
 T. kodakarensis - - - - - IKAAPTSSGSLHPGNIQVIEALGT - D IVLQLSGGT LGHPDPAAGARVQA IDA IMQGI P - - - - -
 A. fulgidus - - - - - IKAMPVSSGGLHPGNLEPVIDALGK - E IVIQGGV LGHPMKA GAKAVQA LDATIISAIP - - - - -
 Thermosynochococcus - - - - - MPGVMAVA SGGTHVWHMPALVEIFGD - DAVLQFGGTLGHPWGNAPGATANRVALEACIQARNEGRDLMREG - - - - -
 Spinacia - - - - - TPGVLPVA SGGTHVWHMPALVEIFGD - DSVLQFGGTLGHPWGNAPGAVANRVALEACVQARNEGRDLAREG - - - - -
 Synechocystis - - - - - MPGVLPVA SGGTHVWHMPALVEIFGD - DSVLQFGGTLGHPWGNAPGATANRVALEACVQARNEGRDLAREG - - - - -
 Synechococcus - - - - - MPGTMPVA SGGTHVWHMPALVEIFGD - DSVLQFGGTLGHPWGNAPGATANRVALEACVQARNEGRDLAREG - - - - -
 Chlamydomonas - - - - - MPGVMPVA SGGTHVWHMPALVEIFGD - DSVLQFGGTLGHPWGNAPGAAANRVALEACTQARNEGRDLAREG - - - - -
 C. necator - - - - - LRKVMPVA SGGTHAGQMHLIHLFGD DVVLQFGGTLGHPWGNAPGAAANRVALEAMV LARNEGRDLINEG - - - - -

Gallionella 2 - - - - - P I E W A K E H K E F A R A F E S F P K D A D K L F P G W R E K L G V H K - - - - -
 R. palustris - - - - - P V E F A K D H R E F A R A F E S F P Q D A D K L Y P N W R A K L K P Q A A - - - - -
 Gallionella - - - - - P I E Y A K T H K E F A R A F E S F P K D G D K L F A G W R E K L G V H K - - - - -
 R. rubrum - - - - - V L D Y A R E H K E L A R A F E S F P G D A D Q I Y P G W R K A L G V E D T R S A L P A - - - - -
 M. burtonii - - - - - I E E Y A K D H K E L A E A I E F Y L N R - - - - -
 T. kodakarensis - - - - - L D E Y A K T H K E L A R A L E K W G H V T P V - - - - -
 A. fulgidus - - - - - L E E H A K Q H P E L Q A A L E K W G R V T P I - - - - -
 Thermosynochococcus G D I I R E A A R W S P E L A A A C E L W K E I K F E F E A Q D T I - - - - -
 Spinacia N T I I R E A T K W S P E L A A A C E V W K E I K F E F P A M D T V - - - - -
 Synechocystis G D I I R E A G K W S P E L A A A L D L W K E I K F E F E T M D K L - - - - -
 Synechococcus N D V I R E A C R W S P E L A A A C E L W K E I K F E F E A M D T L - - - - -
 Chlamydomonas G D V I R S A C K W S P E L A A A C E V W K E I K F E F D T I D K L - - - - -
 C. necator P E I L R D A A R W C A P L R A A L D T W G D I T F N Y T P T D T S D F V P T A S V A - - - - -

5432

Q392

540

530

520

510

500

490

480

470

460

450

440

430

420

410

400

V323

390

380

370

360

350

340

330

320

310

300

Supp. Fig. 2. Volcano plots of proteomics data comparing samples taken at generation 0 (before induction with aTc) and **(A)** generation 3.7 and **(B)** generation 8.6 in continuous light and a gas feed of 5% CO₂, 95% N₂, 0% O₂. Proteins are labeled with their gene name in case they belong to operons which are known to be of relevance for the carbon-concentrating mechanisms (compare Supp. Table 3). In addition, *dCas9*, *rbcS* and *rbcL* as well *cbbM* are labeled.

Supp Fig. 2. Plot of all weighted mean log₂FC values of all CbbM variants over time, normalized to time point generation 0. The base variant and inactive mutant K214R (K200R when strep-tag is excluded) are highlighted, all other variants shown in light gray.

Supp. Fig. 3 (A) Comparison of the relative solvent accessibility of residues and the average normalized fitness score for all exchanges at that position. The dashed line gives the result of a linear regression between both variables. **(B)** Comparison of the conservation at different residue positions as determined by the EVcouplings web server and the average normalized fitness score. The dashed line gives the result of a linear regression between both variables. For both panels, Pearson's r is given as a small inset.

Supp. Fig. 5. (A) Protein structure of the CbbM Enzyme showing the residues G396-I414 (Dark blue) and tunnels (blue and brown) running from the surface to the active site. (B) Residues V323 (pink) and W114 (green) constrain tunnels between the surface (brown) and the active sites (blue). The magnesium ion in the active site is visualized by a red sphere. (C). Residue W114 at the dimer interface constricts a tunnel spanning the entire enzyme, connecting the two active sites (blue). (D) Mutation W144K opening up the tunnels connecting the two active sites. Active sites are marked by the orange K200 residue in panel C and D.

Supp. Fig. 6. Solubility assay of selected variants using western blot with an anti-Strep primary antibody (**A**) and load control via SDS-PAGE (**B**). The first column to the left, for each group, is a protein ladder displaying the size of nearby markers. (**C**) Abundance of each CbbM variant in *Synechocystis* measured by LC/MS.

Supp Fig. 7 Correlation of zero-shot predictors (related to Fig. 3). (A) EVcouplings and DeepSequence (Pearson's $r_{sat}=0.80$ for saturational library and $r_{comb}=0.59$ for combinatorial library) (B) EVcouplings and MSA Transformer (ensemble) (Pearson's $r_{sat}=0.73$ for saturational library and $r_{comb}=0.59$ for combinatorial library)

Supp Fig. 8 zero-shot predictions (related to Fig. 3). (A) EVcouplings (B) DeepSequence (C) MSA Transformer (ensemble). In all panels: r_{comb} gives the Pearson correlation between the zero-shot predictor with the experimentally measured values of the combinatorial library, r_{sat} with the experimentally measured values for the saturation library.

Supp. Fig 9. Correlation of experimental fitness of combinatorial mutants of CbbM_base and prediction of fitness using three zero-shot predictors, when fitness data from V323 exchanges are excluded. **(A)** EVcouplings **(B)** Deep Sequence and **(C)** MSA Transformer.

Supp. Fig. 10. Correlation of experimental fitness of combinatorial mutants of CbbM_base and prediction of fitness using (A) the additive model, (B, C) Protein NPT, which was trained on single-site exchange fitness data. Predictions are shown, including (B) and excluding (C) fitness from V323 exchanges.

Supp Fig. 11. Growth of selected mutants and Base variant in low CO₂ and in nitrogen. (A) Growth at 1 % CO₂ in air, 50 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and 30 °C. (B) Growth of variants in multicultivator at 5 % CO₂, 95 % N₂, at 50 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and 30 °C. For both cultivations, starting OD_{730nm} was 0.05, and the growth test was started ~ 96 h after aTc addition.

Supp Fig. 12. Thermal melting curves of selected CbbM variants expressed in and purified from *E. coli* as determined by nanoDSF.

Supp Fig. 13. Volcano plots of proteomics data comparing the Ad1 strain (A) and CbbM_WT strain (B) with the Base variant 100 h after induction with aTc. The strains were grown in continuous light and a gas feed of 5% CO₂, 75% N₂, 20% O₂. Proteins are labeled with their gene name in case they were significantly changed.

Supp Fig. 14. Oxygen evolution rates in $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \mu\text{g Chl-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ for selected strains measured using a Clark-type electrode at ~ 100 hours after induction with $2 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ aTc induction. Strains were grown at $50 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, 30°C and $5\% \text{CO}_2$, $75\% \text{N}_2$, $20\% \text{O}_2$. The oxygen levels were measured in darkness for the first five minutes. At 5 min the light was turned on at an intensity of $100 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. At 10 minutes $20 \mu\text{M DCMU}$ was added to stop water splitting and O_2 production. **(A)** Oxygen consumption rate during the first five minutes in darkness. **(B)** Net Oxygen evolution rate during the light period **(C)** Oxygen consumption rate after the addition of $20 \mu\text{M DCMU}$. **(D)** Full oxygen evolution procedure.

Supp. Table 1: All 71 positions included in the deep mutational sequencing (DMS) part of the library. Amino acid positions are given for the protein sequence without N-terminal Strep tag (column “no N-Strep”) and with N-terminal Strep tag (column “with N-Strep”). A small x indicates if an exchange was included based on EVmutation (column “EV”) or DeepSequence (column “DS”) predictions. For potentially acetylated lysines, the amino acids in close proximity which triggered the inclusion in the library are given (column “K”). Several amino acid positions were included for various other reasons (column “various”).

no N-Strep	with N-Strep	EV	DS	K	various
K13	K27			E	
K19	K33			N	
K29	K43		x		
I31	I45	x	x		
T77	T91		x		
V84	V98	x	x		
K85	K99	x	x		
F90	F104	x	x		
V92	V106	x			
N109	N123		x		
H112	H126	x	x		
W114	W128	x			
S115	S129		x		
L118	L132		x		
H127	H141	x	x		
Q128	Q142	x			
L136	L150	x	x		
M140	M154	x	x		
V142	V156		x		
K144	K158			R, F	
A150	A164		x		

N154	N168	x	x	
K200	K214			negative control
E214	E228		x	
V215	V229	x	x	
M217	M231	x		
K219	K233	x		
A230	A244	x		
Q233	Q247		x	
Y245	Y259	x	x	
K247	K261		x	
H251	H265	x	x	
D254	D268	x		
F255	F269	x	x	
V256	V270	x	x	
A261	A275	x		
K262	K276		x	
A281	A295		x	
E289	E303		x	
Y308	Y322		x	
K309	K323			Y, S
M312	M326		x	
M314	M328		x	
D315	D329		x	
Y319	Y333		x	
L322	L336		x	
V323	V337	x		
M326	M340		x	

M331	M345	x	x	
H344	H358		x	
G345	G359		x	
K346	K360	x	x	
Y365	Y379		x	
K367	K381		x	Q
Q392	Q406	x	x	
G397	G411		x	
N398	N412			literature
N401	N415			literature
C403	C417		x	
I411	I425		x	
A415	A429		x	
G418	G432	x	x	
I419	I433	x		
K429	K443			S, W
S430	S444	x		
S432	S446	x	x	
K439	K453			T
K442	K456			E
K453	K467			D
K457	K471			D
K465	K479			E

Supp. Table 2: Composition of the library used for growth competition. The number of expected variants according to the library design are compared to the number of variants and number of barcodes observed in the *Synechocystis* mutant pool used for experiments. Base variant: CbbM(WT) with exchanges A230E and G422R, variant underlying the complete library design. “Spontaneous” describes variants which occurred spontaneously. The count of spontaneous variants were not included in the total of the number of observed variants. If spontaneous variants are included, the total number of observed variants is 13,966.

Library part	Expected number variants	Observed number variants (% of expected)	Number barcodes (average per variant)
Base variant	1	1 (100.0)	30 (30.0)
Combinatorial higher-order variants	16,178	12,708 (78.6)	25,793 (2.0)
Saturational	1,349	1,223 (90.7)	4,566 (3.7)
Spontaneous	-	34 (-)	69 (2.0)
Total	17,528	13,932 (79.5)	30,459 (2.2)

Supp. Table 3: Number of variants with a higher fitness value than the library base variant in **(A)** 5% CO₂, 95% N₂, 0% O₂, continuous light **(B)** 5% CO₂, 75% N₂, 20% O₂, continuous light cultivation conditions. Using the Wilcoxon-Rank test, *p* values were calculated by comparing the fitness values of barcodes associated with a specific variant and fitness values of barcodes associated with the base variant. These *p* values were adjusted for multiple testing using Benjamini-Hochberg. Percentages given after the total number of variants are referring to the total number of observed variants, i.e. the 13,966 variants that include spontaneously occurring variants.

(A) Growth condition: 5% CO₂, 95% N₂, 0% O₂, continuous light

Library part	Variants with a higher fitness value than the base variant (percentage of respective part of library)	Variants with a higher fitness value and adjusted <i>p</i> < 0.05 (percentage of respective part of library)
Combinatorial	1,059 (8.3)	93 (0.7)
Saturational	291 (23.8)	87 (7.1)
Spontaneous	1 (2.9)	0 (0.0)
Total	1,351 (9.7)	180 (1.3)

(B) Growth condition: 5% CO₂, 75% N₂, 20% O₂, continuous light

Library part	Variants with a higher fitness value than the base variant (percentage of respective part of library)	Variants with a higher fitness value and adjusted <i>p</i> < 0.05 (percentage of respective part of library)
Combinatorial	1,248 (9.8)	144 (1.1)
Saturational	333 (27.2)	135 (11.0)
Spontaneous	3 (8.8)	0 (0.0)
Total	1,584 (11.3)	280 (2.0)

Supp. Table 4: Proteomics data comparing samples taken at generation 4 or 8 compared samples taken at generation 0, i.e. before addition of aTc. Log 2 fold changes (Log2FC) are marked in bold and color if the corresponding adjusted p value (adj. p) is below 0.01. Data for a subset of proteins is shown. The complete data set is available online.

			Generation 4/ Generation 2		Generation 8/ Generation 2	
	Locus tag	Gene name	Log2FC	adj. p	Log2FC	adj. p
dCas9	<i>NA</i>	<i>dCas9</i>	2.51	2.6E-04	2.46	2.9E-04
Rubisco	<i>slr0009</i>	<i>rbcL</i>	-3.81	2.97E-04	-4.97	7.06E-05
Rubisco	<i>slr0012</i>	<i>rbcS</i>	-3.77	3.54E-04	-5.28	6.87E-05
Carbonic anhydrase	<i>slr1347</i>	<i>ccaA</i>	-1.27	1.98E-04	-1.54	7.06E-05
Carboxysome	<i>sll1028</i>	<i>ccmK2</i>	1.53	6.62E-02	1.30	9.61E-02
Carboxysome	<i>sll1029</i>	<i>ccmK1</i>	1.68	9.49E-04	1.80	5.63E-04
Carboxysome	<i>sll1030</i>	<i>ccmL</i>	2.21	1.49E-02	3.21	2.79E-03
Carboxysome	<i>sll1031</i>	<i>ccmM</i>	-1.87	1.28E-04	-2.32	5.02E-05
NdhR regulon	<i>sll1594</i>	<i>ndhR</i>	1.01	1.60E-03	0.93	2.30E-03
NdhR regulon	<i>sll1732</i>	<i>sll1732</i>	1.00	4.10E-01	2.06	9.24E-02
NdhR regulon	<i>sll1733</i>	<i>ndhD3</i>	3.74	2.88E-05	3.88	2.59E-05
NdhR regulon	<i>sll1734</i>	<i>cupA</i>	3.18	1.90E-05	3.57	6.87E-06
NdhR regulon	<i>sll1735</i>	<i>sll1735</i>	1.84	1.65E-03	1.66	2.57E-03
NdhR regulon	<i>slr1512</i>	<i>sbtA</i>	3.49	1.28E-05	3.99	4.14E-06
NdhR regulon	<i>slr1513</i>	<i>sbtB</i>	3.09	3.44E-03	3.38	2.26E-03
NdhR regulon	<i>slr2011</i>	<i>slr2011</i>	-0.44	7.21E-01	-0.15	8.92E-01

Supp. Table 5: Variants of CbbM_base with the highest normalized fitness score, which are better than the base variant and which were significantly better than the base variant ($p_{adj} < 0.05$) under all three conditions. “Product of normed values” gives the product of the normalized fitness scores under all three conditions. Variants underlying the combinations used for ProteinNPT predictions are marked by an asterisk (*). Note that variants numbering includes a 14-residue N-terminal Strep tag (e.g. W128I is W114I when excluding Strep tag).

Variant	Normalized fitness score			adjusted p value compared to library base variant			Product of normed values
	5% CO ₂ , 95% N ₂ , 0% O ₂	5% CO ₂ , 75% N ₂ , 20% O ₂	LD, 5% CO ₂ , 75% N ₂ , 20% O ₂	5% CO ₂ , 95% N ₂ , 0% O ₂	5% CO ₂ , 75% N ₂ , 20% O ₂	LD, 5% CO ₂ , 75% N ₂ , 20% O ₂	
H126N*	1.23	1.97	1.92	2.52E-02	2.54E-02	7.02E-03	4.64
H126M	1.23	1.96	1.80	8.49E-03	7.05E-05	1.21E-04	4.33
W128I*	1.42	1.98	1.39	2.14E-04	1.37E-04	1.48E-02	3.91
K360I*	1.40	1.98	1.38	4.58E-08	1.72E-07	8.57E-05	3.82
K360M	1.30	1.75	1.55	7.49E-05	4.32E-05	1.86E-04	3.53
Q142D*	1.29	1.89	1.41	6.87E-03	1.00E-03	1.12E-03	3.41
K233C*	1.22	1.81	1.45	6.48E-03	6.05E-04	3.52E-03	3.20
H358C*	1.29	1.91	1.30	2.13E-04	1.53E-06	1.88E-03	3.18
K360L	1.23	1.67	1.53	2.52E-02	2.54E-02	7.02E-03	3.14
H358L	1.31	1.88	1.26	7.80E-05	1.75E-06	1.46E-02	3.13
K99N*	1.20	1.55	1.58	2.04E-02	8.60E-03	1.55E-03	2.94
K360C	1.29	1.70	1.26	6.63E-04	2.28E-04	1.48E-02	2.76
Y333V*	1.21	1.77	1.25	2.88E-03	5.63E-06	4.21E-03	2.69
H126G	1.17	1.35	1.58	2.38E-04	6.70E-03	4.81E-06	2.50
M154E,K261A,Q406D,S446T*	1.27	1.46	1.33	1.31E-02	2.54E-02	3.78E-02	2.47
Q142E	1.12	1.58	1.37	4.63E-02	6.57E-03	6.83E-03	2.43
M345Q*	1.20	1.55	1.30	4.41E-04	7.87E-06	8.94E-04	2.42

F104V*	1.22	1.49	1.32	9.00E-04	6.05E-04	9.90E-03	2.40
V98Q*	1.20	1.59	1.23	6.85E-03	6.57E-03	3.06E-02	2.36
K261A,H26 5A,Q406D, S446I*	1.22	1.43	1.34	3.71E-02	2.54E-02	2.55E-02	2.34
K99T	1.17	1.35	1.28	1.59E-02	4.12E-03	3.87E-02	2.01
K233L	1.14	1.37	1.28	6.85E-03	1.87E-02	7.02E-03	2.00
M345V	1.14	1.17	1.20	4.44E-02	4.91E-02	2.60E-02	1.61

Supp. Table 6: List of all 11 selected mutants created using ProteinNPT. The mutations are on top of the base variant (e.g. also contains S162P and G422R). Note that variants numbering includes a 14-residue N-terminal Strep tag (e.g. W128I is W114I when excluding Strep tag).

Name	Mutations
ML1	F104V:H126N:Q142D:K261A:H265A:K360I:Q406D:S446I
ML2	K99N:F104V:H126N:Q142D:K261A:H265A:K360I:Q406D:S446I
ML3	V98Q:F104V:W128I:Q142D:K261A:H265A:K360I:Q406D:S446I
ML4	H126N:Q142D:K261A:H265A:Q406D:S446I
ML5	V98Q:F104V:H126N:Q142D:K261A:H265A:Y333V:M345Q:H358C:Q406D:S446I
ML6	H126N:Q142D:K261A:H265A:Y333V:Q406D:S446I
ML7	W128I:Q142D:K261A:H265A:Q406D:S446I
ML8	V98Q:F104V:H126N:Q142D:K233C:K261A:H265A:Y333V:Q406D:S446I
ML9	V98Q:F104V:H126N:Q142D:K233C:K261A:H265A:K360I:Q406D:S446I
ML10	V98Q:K99N:F104V:H126N:W128I:Q142D:K261A:H265A:H358C:K360I:Q406D:S446I
ML11	V98Q:K99N:F104V:H126N:W128I:K261A:H265A:K360I:Q406D:S446I